
GOVERNANCE OF A DAO FOR FACILITATING DIALOGUE ON HUMAN-ALGORITHM INTERACTION AND THE IMPACT OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES ON SOCIETY

A PREPRINT

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June 24, 2023

ABSTRACT

Human-algorithm interaction is a crucial issue for humanity in light of the impacts of the recent release of ChatGPT3 and 4, among others. These advanced chatbots provoked a worldwide debate in March/2023, when a manifesto signed by several stakeholders was published and widely discussed in the media and academia. This work assumes that human-algorithm interactions are influenced by a context of diverse interests and perspectives, which adds high complexity to the problem. Therefore, this work proposes a solution to enable the effective participation of stakeholders from different domains and society in a constructive dialogue, using digital platforms as a medium. Inspired by the successful governance of the Internet infrastructure ecosystem, the proposal involves the creation of an Autonomous Decentralized Organization (DAO) implemented in the blockchain environment of the Ethereum network. However, before implementing the DAO, it is necessary to build a knowledge base, that is, an ontology, which guides its development in a safe and adequate way. A preliminary version of this knowledge base was manually built using Protégé with over 4,000 axioms.

Keywords internet infrastructure · web3 · ontology · machine learning · blockchain · decentralized computing · decentralized science

1 Introduction

This paper presents the first results of a proposal outlined in a previous article. The proposal involved brainstorming the creation of an environment for teachers, researchers, thinkers, and other stakeholders to govern artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms and data [1].

The main motivation for proposing the creation of this environment was the complexity of the problem. Regulating or establishing rules for AI algorithm developers is a huge task that requires a debate among a diverse group of stakeholders.

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This is because it involves ethical, social, human, technical, private and public policy issues, among many other areas of human knowledge. Moreover, it is a long debate that requires proper organization to ensure the persistence of the facts produced by a multitude of stakeholders, who represent humanity as a whole.

A problem of similar complexity can be considered: the protocols that ensure the proper functioning and dynamic nature of the Internet over time (past, present, and future). This example comes from the ecosystem surrounding the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF). Thousands of stakeholders meet in person three times a year and continue to work persistently through email working groups for the rest of the year. It is a large and effective organization that ensures the functioning of the Internet as we know it today.

The Internet, with its undeniable importance to humanity, justifies the existence of its own ecosystem [2]. Governance of AI algorithms is a more complex issue than the Internet. Records show that governance of AI algorithms is indeed more complex than the Internet because it involves implications that are not only offensive but also deadly to human beings. In general, regardless of the application, these systems are considered a black box, resulting in asymmetric information between their developers and their consumers [3]. One of the saddest examples highlighting the consequence of this asymmetry is the design of the MCAS⁵ system on the Boeing 737 MAX, which led to two accidents with 346 deaths in October 2018 (Lion Air) and March 2019 (Ethiopian Airlines). When the angle of attack sensor failed, the built-in algorithms forced the plane to lower its nose, resisting repeated attempts by confused pilots to turn the nose up. Ben Shneiderman, in his book *Human-Centered AI* [4], comments on the two Boeing 737 MAX crashes and considers that the future of these AI algorithms is human-centered. They should primarily become super tools that amplify human abilities and empower people in remarkable ways while ensuring human control. Ben named these algorithms HCAI, an acronym for the title of his book.

There are countless other applications, both using AI and not, that behave disproportionately. A detailed description of the so-called algorithmic biases can be found in Safiya Noble's book, *Algorithms of Oppression*, and in other sources [5] [6] [7].

Asymmetric information, biases, and other pertinent issues are concerning developers, researchers, and other interested parties as they try to figure out what is missing [8]. Perspectives associated with ethics [9] [10] [11] [12] [13], regulations [14] [15] [16] [17] [18], governance [19] [20] [21] [22] [23] [3] [24] and many other issues [25] [26] [27] [28] [29] [30] [31] [32] [33] are on the agenda of all stakeholders in search of appropriate alternatives. For example, these issues are widely discussed in Shneiderman's book *Human-Centered AI* [4]. There is extensive literature on the topic presented in the unpublished work that gave rise to the approaches in this article [1].

If we had as strong a motivation as the Internet does, with its immense global reach, the IETF model with its broad stakeholder participation (as seen in Figure 1) could be a solution that would certainly address the issues involving algorithm and data governance.

There are recent signs in AI activities that suggest a growing understanding of the technology by the world's population. This is due to the immense success of ChatGPT, a tool that is popularizing AI and expanding its prominence. This has occurred at an unimaginable speed despite ChatGPT's own limitations in natural language understanding, its reliance on training data, and the possibility of biases. In addition to ChatGPT and other generative AIs, there is the fact that they can propagate biases. Generative AIs are influenced by their training data, which can lead to biased or discriminatory responses. The danger increases with the possibility of the training data being influenced during interaction with its users, i.e., groups with ulterior motives can influence the training data. The refinement of generative AIs is leading to an expansion of their capabilities, including the use of multimodal resources such as ChatGPT-4⁶ and DALL-E 2⁷. In fact, the community involved believes that after such recent releases, we are in for a significant shift in AI. Bill Gates, for example, reacts through a seven-chapter document entitled "The Age of AI has begun" [35]. In Chapter 7, he concludes with "The Age of AI is filled with opportunities and responsibilities." Other concerns come from neuroscientist Miguel Nicolelis. In his most recent book, "The true creator of everything: How the human brain sculpted the universe as we know it" [36], he exposes in the final two chapters the serious risks that humanity will face in the coming years as a result of our increasing interaction and dependence on digital systems. This establishes a true symbiosis that can deeply affect the brain through the phenomenon of neural plasticity. Basically, almost continuous coexistence with computers can affect the way the brain works and, in the limit, turn us into mere digital zombies. Moreover, one cannot forget the stories that are told again and again about famous and recent generative AIs [37].

This work proposes the creation of a DAO called GHAlIA DAO⁸ as an original governance mechanism. To develop this proposal, the authors created a knowledge base about DAOs, which is available, including its updates, in a

⁵Acronym for Manoeuvring Characteristics Augmentation System

⁶<https://openai.com/product/gpt-4>

⁷<https://openai.com/product/dall-e-2>

⁸<https://ghaia.pt>

Figure 1: Internet Governance Ecosystem. Source: [34]

public environment of the Open Science Framework (OSF) [38]. Additionally, this work proposes the creation of the GHAIA DAO to support an environment for debate and registration of stakeholder opinions on issues involving the regulation of AI algorithms and data, as well as issues involving human-algorithm interactions. These issues are widely discussed in the Cátedra Oscar Sala Chair⁹ at IEA-USP¹⁰, whose holder is Prof. Dr. Virgílio Almeida (ORCID: 0000-0001-6452-0361¹¹).

In addition to this Introduction section, this paper discusses DAOs and their variety of governance in Section 2. In Section 2.1 the knowledge base built on Protégé, a free and open-source ontology editor and framework for building intelligent systems [39], is presented. This section also displays alternatives for using this knowledge base, in particular, guidance on the use of the *SPARQL* language as a tool for ontology searches [40, 41]. In Section 5, the proposal for the creation of the GHAIA DAO is presented, which includes an original governance mechanism. Section 8 addresses the conclusions of this stage of the work and recommends future activities to follow. Finally, the bibliography is provided.

2 DAOs

A Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) is a form of organization based on blockchain technology that is generally governed by its members, who hold tokens [42]. Tokens, a type of cryptocurrency (among other meanings), can be acquired or received in some form by any person. As the owner of these tokens, the person gains the right to vote on matters directly related to the governance of the DAO. The governance rules of DAOs are characterized through computer programs known as smart contracts, which are executed and validated within the blockchain of the Ethereum network through a resource called the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM). The features of smart contracts, such as a distributed blockchain database, cause the rules of the organization to be enforced by the very code that defines the DAO, thus making it self-governed.

Therefore, DAOs are different from traditional organizations because they are self-governing and function autonomously in a decentralized manner without the need for intermediaries. In contrast, traditional organizations are subject to rights and responsibilities defined by the legal system of the environment in which they operate.

⁹<https://bit.ly/cos-usp>

¹⁰<http://www.iea.usp.br/>

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2.1 Getting to know implemented DAOs in detail through ontologies

There are many types and functions performed by DAOs. As of April 2023, approximately 150 DAOs have been implemented on the Ethereum network. Due to the diversity of implementations, it was decided to create a knowledge base (or ontology), referred to as KB, to understand and maintain permanent information about all the DAOs. To create this knowledge base, the Protégé software was used [39]. Protégé, developed by Stanford University¹², is a free and open-source ontology editor and knowledge management system.

Two ontologies were created using different techniques. Both are available in the public environment of the project on the Open Science Framework (OSF) [38]. We separated from these two, the one that best represented the expected knowledge. It was named *decom.ttl*, and is detailed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Features of the decom.owl ontology, with 4,004 axioms

The *.ttl* extension, named Turtle, is a syntax for expressing the set of axioms represented in OWL in a text file and is appropriate for display on the Web [43].

To develop the ontology, its scope in the domain of DAOs was first identified. The figures 3, 4 and 5 characterize the main terms of the ontology proposed.

Figure 3: Acronyms that will appear in the development of the proposed ontology.

The ontology resulting from these studies is available on the GHAIA DAO website¹³.

3 How to Search the Knowledge Base

Once the KB is complete with a substantial number of axioms, the main human interest turns to searching the KB. One tool for this is the well-known SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL) [44] [45] [46]. Protégé

¹²<https://protege.stanford.edu/>

¹³<https://ghaia.pt/kb/decom.ttl>

Figure 4: Ontology to be implemented in Protégé.

Figure 5: Complement to the Ontology in the figure above, identifying the various tools for creating DAOs.

provides facilities for using SPARQL, as does Apache Jena¹⁴. In addition to these two examples, DBpedia¹⁵ and Wikidata¹⁶ provide public interfaces to SPARQL, among many others. In all the tools used except Protégé, the URLs <https://ghaia.pt/kb/decom.owl> or <https://ghaia.pt/kb/decom.ttl> are used as the entry point. In Protégé, SPARQL acts on the loaded ontology.

¹⁴<https://jena.apache.org/tutorials/sparql.html>

¹⁵<http://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/dataspace/doc/dav/wiki/Main/VOSSPARQL>

¹⁶<https://w.wiki/rL>

Protégé offers other resources to search the ontology produced through it. For example, the OntoGraph provides images such as the one shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Graphical view of knowledge base DAOs

4 An AI Algorithms and their biases

The Catedra Oscar Sala focused on “Algorithms, artificial intelligence (AI), robots and machines operated by algorithms that increasingly mediate our social, cultural, economic and political interactions” in its Human-Algorithm Interactions Project.

For the Catedra¹⁷, "there are three basic motivations for the proposed focus of the Catedra Oscar Sala in 2022/23:

1. There are many different types of algorithms in operation that play an increasing role in society and in the daily activities of citizens.
2. The complexity of algorithms and systems integrating multiple algorithms is increasing rapidly. New models and massive amounts of data make these algorithms and systems opaque, making it very difficult to understand their behavior.
3. Understanding the social, political, and economic impacts, whether positive or negative, is a research challenge.

Prof. Virgilio anticipated a global concern over opaque algorithms, mostly those of AI. This has proven to be an issue of high priority for humanity, culminating very recently with a manifesto produced by the Future of Life Institute regarding concerns over ChatGPT (Chat Generative Pre-trained Transformer) [47]. The manifesto proposes a six-month moratorium on training it and other similar algorithms, especially those using large language models [48].

Books, scientific papers, newspaper articles, and many other forms of expression have laid out their opinions, concerns, and recommendations to counter the unregulated invasion of algorithms with biases of all kinds. There have been serious offenses and even criminal offenses. However, the texts before the manifesto described in the previous paragraph were intense.

In addition to the above documents, many others, especially recent ones with their references, address the same issue [49] [50] [51] [52] [53] [54] [55] [56] [57] [58] [59] [60] [61].

The proposal of the Catedra Oscar Sala for activities for the year 2022/2023 showed its immense academic diversity. In the opinion of the authors, it is a subject of quite high complexity deserving special attention and continuous debate with the participation of a large number of stakeholders. An adequate form of governance, copying the proposal implemented in the IETF by the Internet Society (ISOC), is suggested.

¹⁷<https://bit.ly/cosvirgilioalmeida>

Therefore, based on ISOC's concerns about the ecosystem that governs the Internet, the authors propose the creation of a DAO named GHAIA DAO, which is presented in the following sections.

5 GHAIA DAO Constitution

One of the main concerns of a DAO is its governance, which must be efficient and democratic [62] [63]. The first DAOs set out to admit that their governance was done by their members, who held the tokens. A DAO member would have a number of votes equivalent to the number of tokens they owned. As time went on, it became apparent that those interested in controlling the votes and inducing the governance to work the way they wanted could easily do this by buying enough tokens. This began to happen, and such participants were called whales.

In an attempt to improve the governance process, a voting scheme was used in which each participant would have one vote. The whales were unrelenting and created phantom participants or used proxies to increase their participation power. A new scheme was adopted, the so-called quadratic scheme, ensuring that voting would be decentralized [64]. In this proposal, voting continues per member, but each member receives a number of votes equal to twice the number of their tokens, which can additionally be used in voting. Suppose that member *A* has 5 tokens and member *B* has 10 tokens. Then, *A* will have 10 votes that they can use 5 as credits to vote on one proposal and 5 credits to vote on another proposal. Member *B* will have 20 votes and can use 10 credits for one proposal and 10 credits for another proposal. The member who has more tokens can spend their votes on a proposal, but if the other member has more members supporting their proposal, they can win the vote. Quadratic voting allows users to "pay" for additional votes on a given proposal to more strongly express their support for certain issues. This results in voting outcomes aligned with the highest willingness to participate (or pay), rather than just the outcome preferred by the majority, regardless of the intensity of individual preferences. This question about democracy exercised in a DAO leads to the fundamental dilemmas of societies with their paradoxes and behavior of the individuals who constitute them, particularly in those who live in societies in which democratic institutions function [65].

Other DAOs, adopting one of the above criteria, establish a Governance Council that will look after their governance for a previously agreed period.

6 The GHAIA DAO

DeSci (Decentralized Science) is a recent movement that aims to use new technologies, such as blockchain or the Web3 environment¹⁸, to address some of the problematic points of scientific research, silos, and bottlenecks. It is an open and global alternative to the modern scientific system that faces many challenges. It extends the idea of open science, allowing scientists to raise funds, share experimental data, and get ideas. One of the most interesting examples is that of a DeSci to tailor peer review [66] [67] [66] [68] [69] [70].

The GHAIA DAO is a DeSci and will use ORCID ID for its governance, which is described in the following section.

6.1 ORCID

ORCID stands for Open Researcher and Contributor ID and is a global, non-profit, fee-supported organization of its member organizations. They form a community built and governed by a Board of Directors representative of members with broad stakeholder representation [71].

The ORCID ID is a unique, persistent, free identifier for individuals to use while engaging in research, scholarship, and innovation activities. ORCID offers a set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs).

As of early April 2023, the statistics of ORCID¹⁹ indicated something like nine million four hundred and ten researchers enrolled, spread across 56 countries. Brazil was the third country with the most registrants (361,900), after the United States (794,493) and China (412,925).

6.2 The Governance of the GHAIA DAO

When implemented, the GHAIA DAO will be a DeSci that provides a multi-disciplinary discussion environment among stakeholders in the issues surrounding algorithmic human interaction. It will follow, in part, the IETF and IRTF²⁰ (Internet Research Task Force) discussion model. The following rules will model the GHAIA DAO:

¹⁸Not a very acceptable generic name given to the blockchain

¹⁹<https://info.orcid.org/orcid-statistics/>

²⁰<https://irtf.org>

1. It will have two types of tokens: OR and NOR, both initially with a value of one (1) USD.
2. Its members will be of two types: those who have an ORCID and those without an ORCID.
3. Stakeholders with an ORCID will receive 1 OR free of charge. The OR is equivalent to 1 NOR, which on the implementation date of the GAIA DAO will be equivalent to one (1) USD. Stakeholders without an ORCID need to purchase NORs at market value to become members.
4. One OR is equivalent to one NOR. ORs are not tradable, but NORs are freely tradable.
5. The holder of an OR will be entitled to receive a NOR twenty-one (21) months after having received the OR without losing the right to vote.
6. The GHAIA DAO treasury must have collateral equivalent to the value of the number of NORs distributed in ORs. In other words, you cannot distribute an OR without having the equivalent collateral in the GHAIA DAO treasury.
7. Participants holding an OR can vote and can be voted for a twenty-one (21) member board, which will handle the governance of the GHAIA DAO.
8. Participants who do not hold an OR, that is, do not have an ORCID, do not have voting rights but can be voted for.
9. Participants with an OR also vote for the Control Council, consisting of seven (7) members whose purpose is to ensure that there are no excesses on the part of the Governance Council. See Figure 7.
10. Outside the blockchain, the Governance Board, through Technical Support, will maintain email lists equivalent to the IETF/IRTF working groups (WGs²¹) and other similarities to make effective debate around Human-Algorithm Interactions.
11. The GHAIA DAO Internet environment should host a repository of documents equivalent to IETF RFCs (Request for Comments) that will be developed by its members.
12. Other rules related to the social and ethical behavior of both participants should be defined.
13. Technical and Operational Support is composed of technical, administrative and other personnel who are adequately remunerated.

Figure 7 displays the proposed governance for the GHAIA DAO.

This figure abstracts from implementation details on the Ethereum network and the Internet resources outside the blockchain that are necessary to meet the goals of the GHAIA DAO.

7 Related Literature

Table 1 references the literature used to understand the mechanism of algorithm and data governance and allows for a comparison of the recommended proposals. Most of these references were originally collected in the proposal prepared as a requirement of the preliminary phase of the Oscar Sala Chair and not published [1].

The references are classified into seven categories and are not exhaustive in the list presented in this proposal:

- (a). **Internet:** These include references that address the topic of Internet governance.
- (b). **Algorithms:** These are references that display AI algorithms in various application areas.
- (c). **DAO:** References that address DAOs and the respective techniques on which they are built (blockchain and cryptocurrencies).
- (d). **Economics:** References that address issues related to the economics of algorithms and their environments.
- (e). **Others:** A set of references that describe the involvement of AI algorithms in subjects such as Bots, Discrimination, Software Engineering, AI, Games, Robotics, and Security.
- (f). **RLiterature:** Literature review papers, including systematic reviews.
- (g). **Social:** Papers that reference the social, ethical, and philosophical aspects of algorithms.

²¹Work Groups

Figure 7: GHAIA DAO's proposed governance structure

8 Conclusions and future work

There is much work to be done to set up the GHAIA DAO. The current unavailability of resources has prevented the implementation of the GHAIA DAO, but it is considered a momentary hindrance. The KB of DAOs proved to be an appropriate solution for learning about DAOs while simplifying their presentation.

In the future, the following tasks were considered mandatory:

- i. ORCID should be informed of the intentions to use the ORCID ID to identify future voting members of the GHAIA DAO.
- ii. The economic model of the GHAIA DAO's operating structure must be formally constructed prior to its establishment. This model, among many other outcomes, must estimate the safe collateral for its initiation. The base parameter for this formulation at the beginning of April 2023 is the 9,410,000 researchers registered in ORCID, plus the costs involved in maintaining Technical and Operational Support. It is hoped that stakeholders in the project can develop papers in this direction.
- iii. After the economic model has been defined and all the operating rules for the DAO have been established, one or more smart contracts will be developed to ensure the self-governance of the GHAIA DAO.
- iv. DAOs are not yet regulated in many countries, which can create legal uncertainty. Interested parties with expertise in law, particularly international law, should study this issue.
- v. The ontology created using Protégé and stored in *decom.ttl* must be evaluated, checked, and compared with other similar ontologies to ensure its validity. However, the manual process of building an ontology can be time-consuming and exhausting, and may not always produce accurate results. As such, it is recommended to use semi-automatic techniques that involve a combination of manual input and automated processes to develop and update the ontology. These techniques, which are constantly being improved, generally involve the use of deep learning and text capture from the web [462, 463, 464, 465].
- vi. A text detailing the use of SPARQL over the two bases should be developed in tutorial form to spread the work developed and useful for the interested community.
- vii. A companion paper presenting the graphics produced extensively by Protégé is available at the OSF of the project²².

²²<https://bit.ly/daoKBinGraphics>

Table 1: Primary and secondary studies. by subject

#	References	Classification
1.	[72],[73],[74],[75],[76],[77],[78],[79],[80],[81],[82],[83],[84],[85],[86]	Internet
2.	[87],[88],[89],[90],[91],[92],[93],[94],[95],[96],[97],[98],[99],[100],[101],[102]	Algorithms
3.	[103],[104],[105],[106],[107],[108],[109],[110],[111],[112],[113],[114],[115]	
4.	[116],[117],[118],[119],[120],[121],[122],[123],[124],[125],[126],[127],[128]	
5.	[129],[130],[131],[132],[133],[134],[135],[136],[137],[138],[139],[140],[141]	
6.	[142],[143],[144],[145],[146],[147],[148],[149],[150],[151],[152],[153],[154]	
7.	[155],[156],[157],[158],[159],[160],[161],[162],[163],[164],[165],[166],[167]	
8.	[168],[169],[170],[171],[172],[173],[174],[175],[176],[177],[178],[179],[180]	
9.	[181],[182],[183],[184],[185],[186],[187],[188],[189],[190],[191],[192],[193]	
10.	[194],[195],[196],[197],[198],[199],[200],[201],[202],[203],[204],[205],[206]	
11.	[207],[208],[209],[210],[211],[212],[213],[214],[215],[216],[217],[218],[219]	
12.	[220],[221],[222],[223],[224],[225],[226],[227],[228],[229]	
13.	[230],[231],[232],[233],[234],[235],[236],[237],[238],[239],[240],[241],[242]	
14.	[243],[244],[245],[246],[247]	Economics
15.	[248],[249],[250],[251],[252],[253],[254],[255],[256],[257],[258],[259],[260]	
16.	[261],[262],[263],[264],[265],[266],[267],[268],[269],[270],[271],[272],[273]	
17.	[274],[275],[276],[277],[278],[279]	Others
18.	[280],[281],[282],[283],[284],[285],[286],[287],[288],[289],[290],[291],[292]	
19.	[293],[294],[295],[296],[297],[298],[299],[300],[301],[302],[303],[304],[305]	
20.	[306],[307],[308],[309],[310],[311],[312],[313],[314],[315],[316],[317],[318]	
21.	[319],[320],[321],[322],[323],[324],[325],[326],[327],[328],[329],[330],[331]	
22.	[332],[333],[334],[335],[336],[337],[338],[339]	
23.	[340],[341],[342],[343],[344],[345],[346],[347],[348],[349],[350],[351],[352]	Governance
24.	[353],[354],[355],[356],[357],[358],[359],[360],[361],[362],[363],[364],[365]	
25.	[366],[367],[368],[369],[370],[371],[372],[373],[374],[375],[376],[377],[378]	
26.	[379],[380],[381],[382],[383],[384],[385],[386],[387],[388],[389],[390],[391]	
27.	[392],[393],[394],[395],[396],[397],[398],[399],[400],[401],[402],[403],[404]	
28.	[405],[406],[407],[408],[409],[410],[411],[412],[413],[414],[415],[416],[417]	
29.	[418],[419],[420],[421],[422],[423],[424],[425],[426],[427],[428],[429],[430]	
30.	[431],[432],[433]	
31.	[434],[435],[436],[437]	
32.	[438],[439],[440],[441],[442],[443],[444],[445],[446],[447],[448],[449],[450]	RLiterature
33.	[451],[452],[453],[454],[455],[456],[457],[458],[459],[460],[461]	Social

- viii. For the success of the project, it is appropriate to have an unlimited presence of stakeholders from the most varied and immense areas of knowledge, including society in general.
- ix. It is expected that the DAO will host interested parties in extending human-algorithm interactions to the context of all digital platforms.

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